

INTRODUCTION OF METHODOLOGICAL USE OF NEW INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES (BASED ON INTERNET RESOURCES) DURING ENGLISH LESSONS

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Annotation: This article deals with modern pedagogical technologies in teaching English and role of the English language as an opportunity to join the world culture, to use the opportunities of the Internet, as well as to work with Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and Use multimedia teaching methods.

Key words: English, pedagogy, learning, multimedia, educational activity.

Informatization of society creates new forms of educational activity. Today, it is generally accepted that young people must be ready for life in the modern information society and have the necessary skills to work with information.

One of the priorities in the modernization of higher education is the active use of new information technologies (NIT). New information technologies, in which the Internet is a leading position, are designed to provide a qualitatively new level of education in higher education. At this stage, most universities are connected to the global Internet and local information networks.

There is a positive trend in the active use of new forms of organization of the educational process in the teaching of foreign languages. Innovative teachers effectively use NIT in foreign language teaching courses. Internet portals for teaching in foreign languages are being created, computer classes are being opened. Video materials are used in the lesson, electronic textbooks are used, virtual tours, video conferences are held. Foreign language teachers are increasingly using project methods with the involvement of computer technology.

The advantages of using the global Internet with the proper organization of students' classroom and extracurricular activities are obvious:

- provides access to giant original media texts;
- orally and written communication;
- to develop the skills of native speakers and the culture of international communication;
- facilitates the solution of a number of didactic tasks (students' vocabulary expands, writing skills improve, etc.);

-students' general outlook expands and a stable motivation to learn foreign languages is formed;

-a student-centered approach to learning is implemented;

Studying a computer science course in high school helps computer skills at the elementary user level in many ways. Experience shows that the majority of students use Word, Excel, Web Design, Power Point, etc. in their educational activities. Thus, all of the above facts show that Internet technology can be considered one of the most effective tools for optimizing learning activities in English classes. In recent years, many works have been written by local and foreign researchers to present the obvious advantages of using NIT in the teaching process. For example, a number of useful recommendations on the safe and efficient use of the Internet are contained in the scientific work of E.S. Polat and M.Yu. Bukharkina. Problems of using media technologies in English lessons are devoted to the work of local researchers (A.A. Novikova, N. P. Ryzhikh, I.M. Khijnyak, etc.). At the same time, the analysis of the studied literature allows us to conclude that the problem of developing a methodological application of Internet resources has not yet been sufficiently studied for their application in the educational process. In this article, we do not claim a detailed analysis of all the problems encountered by students during class and extracurricular activities when using Internet resources. Therefore, it seems expedient to take a brief look at such problems and consider ways to solve them.

The main disadvantages of using the Internet in the educational process include:

-information resources of the Internet education segment are not regulated by law;

- no one for the accuracy and reliability of online information

- not responsible; Many electronic textbooks are properly reviewed

- not held; numerous computer viruses are recovered;

- racism, xenophobia, aggression, etc. on the Internet. there are materials with elements;

Excessive and uncontrolled use of the Internet contributes to the development of Internet addiction. At the same time, modern media is increasingly taking on enlightening functions. Statistics show that students are the most active consumers of the media, especially the Internet, which has become one of the main sources of information for them, a means of understanding the world around them. This creates a very controversial situation. On the one hand, students are quite familiar with modern media technologies. On the other hand, it is difficult for them to navigate in a constantly updated avalanche-like flow of

information. Many are manipulated by the media because they still do not have enough money. Criteria have been developed for a critical assessment of the information transmitted through various media channels. Therefore, young students must be able to work with information arrays presented in both traditional and electronic formats.

In recent years, the concepts of "information literacy", "computer literacy" and "media literacy" / "media competence" have become more common in the scientific literature. We consider it wrong to put an equal sign between these concepts. In our opinion, it is necessary to distinguish them. "Information literacy" refers to the ability and skills to work with information in both traditional and electronic formats. Computer literacy is the ability to work with a computer. The term "media literacy" refers to the ability to work with the media, receive, process, critically analyze, systematize, and create their own media products. As already mentioned, at the current stage of informatization of higher education, intensive application of NIT to teaching practice is underway. From this point of view, the most important work in this direction seems to us to be not only to teach students to search for information, but also to develop the skills of analytical and selective perception of the huge information offered by modern media. Teaching the basics of media literacy. Therefore, already at the initial stage of teaching English, students should develop the ability to work with information provided in electronic format: encyclopedias, textbooks, online reference books, dictionaries, etc. When working with electronic publications of theses and articles on the Internet, students should pay special attention to the observance of copyright and intellectual property.

The most important thing when working with Internet resources is the formation and development of critical thinking skills. In this regard, we share the opinion of Novikova: "Apart from using the Internet as a source of material for learning English, we must help our students to move from the role of a passive consumer to a more active, creative personality. able to find, analyze and transmit information with the help of modern technologies, and I hope that it is quite motivated and designed for the independent development of reading, writing and listening skills" [Novikova, 2004, p.34].

- "sifting" of information (reasoned identification of reliability and false disclosure of information from "rouge" and "shortcuts" reliable facts, etc.);
- removal from the information of the halo of "typicality", "common people",
- "authority";

-critical analysis of the goals, interests of the "agency", that is, the source of information.

After reviewing the local and foreign scientific literature on the use of NIT in the teaching process, we drafted a memorandum for students to work with Internet resources. In this article, its main provisions have been translated into Russian and compiled as follows:

- pay attention to the source of information and the author of the publication;
- to be sure of the scientific objectivity and reliability of the received information;
- to determine the meaning of the value of the media text;
- check and compare several sources of information on the topic;
- Do not believe, but critically analyze the relevance of the information received;
- be vigilant against online propaganda;
- in some cases use a data filter;
- emphasize the main points in the information message;
- to interpret the information (taking into account the direction and purpose of the target). information);
- translate the received information independently;
- property to apply information that is the object of copyright and intellectual property;

Manage your time on the Internet.

As the experience of teaching English shows, the following types of tasks are most effective for developing reading and critical thinking skills:

- determine the list of problems considered in the title of the text;
basic
- to compile a plan of the text emphasizing the ideas;
- read the paragraph and say what words can be used to determine whether the author is (or is not) a professional in this field;
- determine for which audience this text is intended;
- to determine the frequency of use of general scientific terms;
- find examples of confirmation (absence) of known facts in the text;

Logical

- select connectors;
- express your attitude to what you read based on facts, not opinions;
- to annotate the text;

Write an ad based on the material of this text (response article, opinion, etc.)

Undoubtedly, the effectiveness of students 'work with Internet resources depends mainly on the competent organization and coordination of the teacher,

who should focus their efforts on making students' work with Internet resources as useful, informative and safe as possible. First of all, teachers must actively master advanced information technologies and apply them to teaching activities. Selection of students and analytical process of information research, to form the skills of critical perception of information obtained from the Internet. Awareness-raising activities should also be strengthened to emphasize the rules of secure operation and data protection on the Internet. Raise issues with illegal and offensive content. Encourage students to use the Internet not only as a source of information, but also to recommend additional sources of information for learning: encyclopedias, scientific journals, articles, textbooks. In practice, it is advisable to use group forms of information retrieval, followed by exchanges and discussions, which provide a communicative approach to learning a foreign language.

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